

FOOD ALLOCATION AND HEALTH SERVICES AND THE WELFARE AND DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY (PDL) AT BJMP, PARAÑAQUE CITY JAIL

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between food allocation, health services, and Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) welfare and development at BJMP, Parañaque City Jail. It specifically investigated how the quality and accessibility of food and healthcare services affected the physical and psychological wellbeing of PDLs, as well as their rehabilitation and reintegration into society. Using a mixed-method approach, data were collected through surveys and interviews with PDLs and jail personnel. Findings revealed that inadequate food distribution and limited health services negatively impacted the welfare and development of PDLs. A notable aspect of the study was exploring the *Paabot System*, a practice where families send food and necessities to PDLs through delivery services such as Grab. While this system helped supplement the jail's limited provisions and supported the well-being of PDLs, it also raised concerns regarding regulation, fairness, and potential security risks. The study emphasized enhancing this informal system by aligning it with existing jail policies to ensure safe and equitable implementation. It concluded by recommending improvements in policy, increased resource allocation, and the formalization of support systems like the *Paabot System* to ensure humane treatment and better rehabilitation outcomes for PDLs.

Keywords: *Food allocation and Health Services, and Welfare and Development, BJMP Parañaque City Jail*

INTRODUCTION

The humane treatment and overall well-being of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) continue to pose serious challenges within the Philippine correctional system, particularly in congested facilities such as the BJMP Parañaque City Jail. These jails often deal with overcrowding, limited funding, and operational difficulties, resulting in poor food distribution and restricted access to healthcare. Such conditions can severely affect the physical, emotional, and mental health of inmates and reduce their chances of rehabilitation and reintegration into society.

This research supports several key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including SDG 1 – eliminating poverty in all forms; SDG 2 – ending hunger and ensuring food security and proper nutrition; SDG 3 – promoting good health and well-being for people of all ages; and SDG 16 – promoting inclusive, peaceful, and just institutions. These goals emphasize the importance of protecting the rights and well-being of marginalized groups, including PDL.

On a national level, the study is anchored on Republic Act No. 6975, also known as the Department of the Interior and Local Government Act of 1990, which established the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP). This agency is tasked with safeguarding and developing detainees, ensuring their access to proper nutrition, healthcare, and rehabilitation programs.

This study aimed to assess the current state of food provision and health services at BJMP Parañaque City Jail and how these impacted the welfare and development of PDL. It also explored the implementation of the *Paabot System*, a mechanism where families send food and basic items through delivery services. Although this system helped meet the needs of detainees, it also presented challenges regarding fairness, security, and formal regulation. By conducting this research, the authors sought to offer data-based recommendations to improve jail-living conditions, consistent with the BJMP's responsibilities and global human rights and development standards.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. This study investigated the food allocation and health services and the welfare and development of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at BJMP, Parañaque City Jail.
2. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Age
 - 2.2 Sex
 - 2.3 Religious Affiliation
 - 2.4 Civil Status
 - 2.5 Length of Detention?
3. What is the level of food allocation and health services among PDL in terms of:
 - 3.1 Quality of Food
 - 3.2 Quantity of Food
 - 3.3 Quality of Health Services?
4. What is the level of welfare and development of PDLs in terms of:
 - 4.1 Physical Health
 - 4.2 Mental Health
 - 4.3 Emotional Health
5. Is there any significant relationship between food allocation and health services, and the welfare and development of persons deprived of liberty?

HYPOTHESIS

Ho: There is no significant relationship between food allocation and health services and the welfare and development of persons deprived of liberty.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive approach within a quantitative research design. The systematic integration of key components allowed for a coherent and logical strategy to address the research problem effectively. Additionally, this approach provided the necessary structure for gathering, measuring, and analyzing data (Creswell & Creswell, 2021; Babbie, 2020).

The study targeted Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at BJMP, Parañaque City Jail, selected through simple random sampling to ensure a representative sample. A researcher-made survey questionnaire, developed based on existing literature and current jail conditions, was the primary data collection tool. The instrument had three (3) sections: 1) demographic profile, 2) food allocation and health services, and 3) the welfare and development of PDLs. The questionnaire underwent a rigorous validation process with the assistance of field experts, the research adviser, and the Dean, before its final approval by the Research and Development Extension (RDE) unit. Responses were measured using a 4-point Likert Scale.

Data was collected across multiple scheduled visits approved by the jail administration in February 2025, resulting in 286 completed questionnaires. The collected data were encoded into Microsoft Excel and analyzed by a professional statistician. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation were utilized to summarize and interpret key findings of the study.

Furthermore, Spearman's Rho correlation was employed to examine the relationship between demographic variables (age, sex, civil status, religious affiliation, and length of detention) and welfare aspects related to food allocation and health services. Given the ordinal level of measurement and the non-normal distribution of the data, Spearman's Rho was deemed appropriate, as it effectively determined monotonic relationships without assuming normality (Mukaka, 2020; Dancey & Reidy, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Summary of Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Food Allocation and Health Services

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Quality of Food	3.38	0.72	Agree
Quantity of Food	3.37	0.71	Agree
Quality of Health Services	3.40	0.67	Agree
Average Mean	3.38	0.70	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly Agree

Table 1 shows the mean scores and standard deviations for food allocation and health services at BJMP Parañaque City Jail. Overall, respondents reported moderately positive perceptions, with an average mean score of 3.38 (SD = 0.70). Health services received the highest mean (3.40, SD = 0.67), followed by food quality (3.38, SD = 0.72) and food quantity (3.37, SD = 0.71). The relatively low standard deviations indicate consistent responses across participants.

These results align with Mears and Cochran (2020), who stressed that adequate food and healthcare are critical to detainees' well-being and institutional order. Likewise, Wang et al. (2019)

emphasized that poor service provision can lead to malnutrition, illness, and mental distress, underscoring the need for continuous assessment in correctional settings to uphold basic human rights and promote welfare.

Table 2

Summary of Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Welfare and Development of PDL

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Physical Health	3.34	0.69	Agree
Mental Health	3.38	0.65	Agree
Emotional Health	3.41	0.67	Agree
Average Mean	3.38	0.67	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 2 summarizes the average ratings and standard deviations concerning the welfare and development of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) at BJMP Parañaque City Jail. Overall, participants indicated agreement that their physical, mental, and emotional needs are being addressed, reflected in a general mean of 3.38 with a standard deviation of 0.67. Among these aspects, emotional well-being received the highest mean score of 3.41 (SD = 0.67), followed by mental health at 3.38 (SD = 0.65), and physical health at 3.34 (SD = 0.69). The relatively low standard deviation values indicate a stable pattern of responses across the group.

These results align with the findings of Baćak et al. (2020), who highlighted the importance of healthcare and rehabilitation efforts in improving detainees' overall wellbeing and aiding successful reintegration after release. Likewise, Fazel et al. (2019) emphasized that emotional health is critical in rehabilitation, with poor emotional conditions often leading to increased violence and repeated offenses. Their study underlines the necessity of providing adequate mental health support within prison facilities.

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Food Allocation and Health Services and Welfare and Development of PDLs.

Food Allocation and Health Services	Welfare and Development of PDL	Computed r-value	P- value	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
<i>Quality of Food</i>	<i>Physical Health</i>	0.460**	0.000	Reject	Significant
	<i>Mental Health</i>	0.436**	0.000	Reject	Significant
	<i>Emotional Health</i>	0.335**	0.001	Reject	Significant
<i>Quantity of Food</i>	<i>Physical Health</i>	0.463**	0.000	Reject	Significant
	<i>Mental Health</i>	0.436**	0.000	Reject	Significant
	<i>Emotional Health</i>	0.361**	0.000	Reject	Significant
<i>Quality of Health Services</i>	<i>Physical Health</i>	0.650**	0.000	Reject	Significant
	<i>Mental Health</i>	0.462**	0.000	Reject	Significant
	<i>Emotional Health</i>	0.455**	0.000	Reject	Significant

***Correlation is significant if the p-value is \leq to 0.01 level level of significance*

According to the statistics in Table 3, there was a significant connection between food allocation, health services, and the welfare and development of PDL. All three physical, mental, and emotional health indicators have statistically significant associations with food quality, quantity, and quality of health services.

For instance, there was a significant 0.01 association between food quality and physical health, with an r-value of 0.460, mental health with an r-value of 0.436, and emotional health with an r-value of 0.335. Similarly, meal amount correlated with physical, cognitive, and emotional wellbeing, with r-values of 0.463, 0.436, and 0.361, respectively. Furthermore, the quality of healthcare showed even larger relationships, particularly with physical health, with an r-value of 0.650, mental health with an r-value of 0.462, and emotional health with an r-value of 0.455. These findings highlighted the importance of adequate food supply and quality healthcare services in maintaining the well-being

of PDL. Ensuring sufficient nutrition and proper healthcare provision can significantly contribute to their physical strength, mental stability, and emotional resilience while in detention.

The findings clarified that the researchers' hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between food allocation, health services, and the welfare and development of PDL was rejected; hence, all the variables were found significant. The results indicate that food quality, quantity, and availability to healthcare services significantly impacted the PDL's total well-being, including physical, mental, and emotional health.

CONCLUSIONS

Among the 286 respondents in the study conducted at BJMP Parañaque City Jail, the majority were aged 32–38, comprising 24.48% of the sample, followed by those aged 18–24 at 21.98%. A higher percentage identified as Roman Catholic (63.99%), followed by Muslims (22.73%), indicating the religious diversity among the detainees. Most PDLs were single (69.23%), with only 24.83% being married, 3.85% widowed, and 2.10% separated. These findings suggest that a large portion of the detainees may lack immediate family support, which could impact their emotional well-being during incarceration. Regarding the length of detention, 27.97% had been detained for 1–6 months, and 27.62% for 7–12 months, showing that most respondents were still in the early stages of their detention period.

The study revealed generally favorable perceptions of food allocation and health services. The average mean for food allocation was 3.38 with a standard deviation of 0.72, interpreted as "Agree." Among the indicators, "The food provided is nutritious and sufficient" received the highest rating, with a mean score of 3.41. This suggests that PDLs generally consider the food to meet basic nutritional standards. However, some still expressed concerns about the adequacy of meal portions in maintaining energy levels throughout the day. Health services received a slightly higher average mean score of 3.40 with a standard deviation of 0.67, with PDLs agreeing that healthcare providers were competent. The "The healthcare staff are qualified and competent" indicator had the highest mean score of 3.46, showing respondents had a generally positive view of the medical personnel.

As for the welfare and development of PDL, the study found that respondents agreed with the state of their well-being. Physical health had a mean of 3.34, mental health 3.38, and emotional health 3.41, with an overall average mean of 3.38. These scores indicate that while respondents recognized the presence of basic health and emotional programs, there remains a need to improve support systems, especially in addressing stress and anxiety caused by detention. Based on the correlation analysis, the study found significant relationships between food allocation, health services, and the welfare and development of PDL. Specifically, food quality was strongly associated with emotional, mental, and physical health, while health services showed even stronger relationships with all three well-being indicators. These findings support the conclusion that proper nutrition and accessible healthcare services play a crucial role in the overall rehabilitation of PDL.

Based on the findings, the researchers' hypothesis was rejected, which stated that health services have no significant relationship with the welfare and development of Persons Deprived of Liberty.

Recommendations

1. To ensure that every Person Deprived of Liberty (PDL) consistently receives healthy, well-balanced meals, the researchers recommend that the institution establish a disciplined, sustainable feeding program in collaboration with non-government organizations specializing in nutrition. The researchers recommend enhancing and regulating the "Paabot System," which allows families to send food to Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) through delivery services like Grab, in accordance with existing prison rules and security regulations to ensure safety and proper implementation.
2. The researchers recommend the strategic deployment of medical staff within the facility and collaboration with the Local Health Office to conduct regular medical missions, ensuring accessible and adequate healthcare services for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs).
3. The researchers recommend implementing routine health check-up and basic wellness programs to monitor and maintain the physical health of PDLs and to detect and manage health issues early.
4. The researchers suggest introducing recreational activities such as sports, arts and crafts, music sessions, and group games to help alleviate stress, promote social interaction, and improve the emotional and mental well-being of PDLs.
5. The researchers recommend the implementation of consistent and enhanced procedures for food distribution and healthcare services to ensure fairness, accountability, and efficiency throughout the facility. Improved food distribution should include scheduled meal times, equitable portion, nutritional quality, hygienic preparation and delivery methods to better support the health and well-being of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs).
6. The researchers recommend enhancing collaboration with local government units, nongovernmental organizations, and healthcare providers to supplement resources, such as medical and dental mission, and improve access to nutritious food and quality medical care for PDLs.

REFERENCE LIST

- Amon, J. J., Binswanger, I. A., & Dyer, W. J. (2019). Human rights and health care in prisons: A global perspective. *International Journal of Prisoner Health*, 15(4), 241-255. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
- Azel, S., & Baillargeon, J. (2019). The health of prisoners. *The Lancet*, 393(10187), 258–272.
- Baillargeon, J., Binswanger, I. A., & Penn, J. (2019). The effect of incarceration on the health of individuals. *Health Affairs*, 38(10), 1671-1678. www.whijournal.com
- Baylon, J., Santos, R., & Lagmay, C. (2020). Integrated health service delivery in Philippine prisons: Evaluating effectiveness and outcomes. *Philippine Journal of Criminology*, 14(1), 33-48. <https://journals.sagepub.com/>
- Beck, A. J., Adams, P. J., & Dyer, W. J. (2019). Gender differences in mental health among incarcerated populations. *Journal of Correctional Health Care*, 25(3), 299-307. <https://www.tandfonline.com/>
- Binswanger, I. A., Kwan, Z., & Williams, B. A. (2019). Health and health care among prisoners: A national survey. *American Journal of Public Health*, 109(8), 1125-1132. <https://journals.sagepub.com/>

- BioMed Central Bureau of Jail Management and Penology. (n.d.). *BJMP Manual on the Treatment of Persons Deprived of Liberty*. <http://www.bjmp.gov.ph/>
- Carson, E. A., & Pettus-Davis, C. (2019). Addressing food insecurity in correctional facilities: The impact of meal portioning on inmate health. *Journal of Correctional Nutrition*, 17(3), 112-130.
- Carter, R., & Jones, K. (2021). Integrated health services in correctional settings: A review of models and outcomes. *Journal of Correctional Health Care*, 27(2), 115-123. <https://books.google.com.ph/>
- Champion, V. L., & Skinner, C. S. (2008). The Health Belief Model. In *Health Behavior and Health Education: Theory, Research, and Practice* (pp. 45-65). Jossey-Bass. Charles, A., Draper, H., & Gibson, W. (2019). Healthcare provision in correctional facilities: An analysis of accessibility and effectiveness. *International Journal of Prison Health*, 15(4), 328-343.
- Constitution of the Philippines. (1987). <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/constitutions/1987-constitution/>
- Cummings, J. R., Wen, H., & Druss, B. G. (2020). Improving access to mental health services in correctional settings: Current challenges and future directions. *Health Affairs*, 39(3), 504-510. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2019.01056>
- Davis, M., Thompson, H., & Nguyen, R. (2020). Long-term mental health effects of Department of Budget and Management (DBM). (2023). *General Appropriations Act*. <https://www.dbm.gov.ph/>
- Department of Budget and Management. (2024). *General Appropriations Act FY 2024*. Emerald
- Fazel, S., & Baillargeon, J. (2019). The health of prisoners. *The Lancet*, 393(10187), 1741-1753. 663-9
- Fazel, S., & Baillargeon, J. (2020). The health of prisoners. *The Lancet*, 395(10218), 1741-1753. 663-9
- Firth, J., Solmi, M., Wootton, R. E., Vancampfort, D., Schuch, F. B., Hoare, E., & Smith, L. (2019). A meta-review of "lifestyle psychiatry": The role of exercise, smoking, diet and sleep in the prevention and treatment of mental disorders. *World Psychiatry*, 18(3), 288-306. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20672>
- Franco, L. (2019). A longitudinal study on the physical health outcomes of prisoners in high-density facilities. *International Journal of Health and Correctional Systems*, 14(2), 45-56. <https://search.informit.org/>
- Garcia, S. (2020). The effects of social isolation on mental health in prison. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 47(3), 213-221. <https://journals.plos.org/>
- Gini, K. (2024). The impact of macro-environmental factors on business performance. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Kiyentei-Gini/publication/376792903>
- Gonzalez, J., & Torres, M. (2020). The impact of overcrowding and inadequate medical care on physical health in correctional facilities. *Journal of Public Health Policy*, 42(1), 91-104. <https://heinonline.org/>
- Gonzalez, R., Santos, M., & Vega, J. (2020). *The Role of Healthcare in Correctional Facilities: Implications for Detainee Well-Being and Rehabilitation*. *Journal of Correctional Health Research*, 15(3), 210-225.
- Hanes, M., Roberts, K., & Green, T. (2019). Mental health challenges in correctional facilities: Stress, isolation, and coping strategies. *Journal of Correctional Health Care*, 25(3), 210-224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1078345819857209> httpPMC
- International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC). (2018). *Health care in prisons: A guide for health care professionals*. <https://www.icrc.org/en/publication/health-care-prisons-guide-health-care-professionals>
- Jang, S. J., Johnson, B. R., & Kim, Y.-I. (2019). Religious involvement and

- inmate misconduct: A longitudinal study of federal prisoners. *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, 35(4), 905–932.
- Johnson, P., & Lee, S. (2020). ComRepublic Act No. 9173. (2002). Bureau of Jail Management and Penology Act. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2002/10/02/republicact-no-9173/>
- Laerd Statistics. (2020). *Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation using SPSS Statistics*. Retrieved from <https://statistics.laerd.com/statistical-guides/spearmans-rank-order-correlation-statistical-guide.php>
- Liu, Y., Chang, L., & Lee, J. (2021). Emotional health interventions in correctional settings: Impact on rehabilitation and recidivism. *Psychiatric Services and Correctional Mental Health*, 17(3), 232-240. <https://journals.plos.org/>
- Lopez, M., Cruz, R., & Sanchez, J. (2020). Nutrition and physical health: The importance of dietary interventions in prison systems. *International Journal of Food Science & Nutrition*, 71(4), 365-376. <https://journals.plos.org/>
- Marlow, E., White, M. C., & Tulsy, J. P. (2019). Nutrition and health in correctional facilities: Addressing deficiencies to improve outcomes. *Journal of Correctional Health Care*, 25(2), 134-148.
- Martin, D. (2021). Improving physical health in correctional facilities through medical interventions and nutrition. *Prison Health Review*, 8(1), 12-20. <https://link.springer.com/>
- Martinez, D., & Cruz, P. (2019). *Food Quality and Nutrition in Correctional Facilities: The Impact on Physical and Mental Health of Detainees*. *International Journal of Prison Health Studies*, 18(2), 145-160.
- Mbithi, B. (2019). Environmental factors, globalization, and small and medium-scale enterprises performances in Akure Metropolitan, Ondo State, Nigeria. <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/107255/mbithi%20b.pdf?sequence>
- Miller, T., & Harris, R. (2020). The role of mental health services in improving inmate well-being and rehabilitation. *Psychological Services in Correctional Facilities*, 18(1), 4452. <https://link.springer.com/>
- Montford, S., & Brown, L. (2020). The impact of food quality on inmate health and behavior: A review of correctional meal programs. *International Journal of Prisoner Health*, 16(1), 45-61.
- Montford, S., & Brown, L. (2020). The impact of food quality on inmate health and behavior: A review of correctional meal programs. *International Journal of Prisoner Health*, 16(1), 45-61.
- National Institute of Justice. (2020). The impact of incarceration on health and wellbeing. *NIJ Journal*, 282, 1-12. <https://nij.ojp.gov/library/publications>
- Novak, C., & Jacobs, M. (2020). Food scarcity and portioning in prisons: Examining the effects on health and behavior. *International Journal of Prisoner Well-being*, 5(2), 78-95.
- Parker, J., & Smith, L. (2021). A systematic review of mental health interventions in correctional settings: Impact on inmate welfare. *International Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 56(2), 123-136. <https://link.springer.com>
- prehensive health services in prisons: Effects on inmates' health status and rehabilitation. *International Journal of Prison Health*, 8(2), 134-144. <https://journals.plos.org/> PelayoAcademia.edu PMC Prison Policy Initiative [ps://ncchc.org](https://ncchc.org)
- Ramos, M., & Cruz, F. (2020). Emotional support and social engagement as key factors in inmate well being. *Journal of Inmate Support and Rehabilitation*, 29(4), 215224. <https://link.springer.com/>
- Rappler. (2023). Budget for inmates in 2024: P70 daily for food, P15 for medicines. <https://www.rappler.com/philippines/bureau-corrections-food-medicines-budget-prisoners>

- Rodriguez, A., & Mitchell, S. (2020). The importance of emotional health in the rehabilitation process in correctional facilities. *Journal of Correctional Rehabilitation*, 25(1), 65-77. <https://www.ahajournals.org/>
- Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). Historical origins of the Health Belief Model. In *Health Behavior and Health Education: Theory, Research, and Practice* (pp. 1-19). JosseyBass. <https://saudijournals.com/>
- SAMHSA sampling methods). *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), 210–213. <https://doi.org/10.15406/bbij.2017.05.00148>
- Singh, M., & Nino, R. (2021). Integrated health care approaches for correctional facilities: Improving health outcomes. *Prison Health Review*, 7(1), 1726. <https://www.ahajournals.org/>
- Singh, R., & Patel, A. (2020). Health status as a predictor of successful re-entry into society: A study of prison rehabilitation programs. *Journal of Social Reintegration*, 22(1), 32-44. <https://heinonline.org/>
- Stansfield, R. (2020). Religion, identity, and prison experiences: Examining the role of religious affiliation in the correctional system. *The Prison Journal*, 100(5), 678–699.
- Tan, E., & Ramos, P. (2021). Healthcare provision in prisons: A study on inmates' physical health outcomes. *Journal of Correctional Health*, 32(3), 283–298. <https://journals.sagepub.com/>
- Thompson, J. (2020). Health status and rehabilitation success: A study of correctional health outcomes. *Journal of Rehabilitation and Health*, 34(2), 4556. <https://journals.sagepub.com/>
- Tiu, A., & Rodriguez, C. (2020). Budget constraints and food quality in Philippine jails. *Philippine Journal of Criminology*, 13(1), 23-30. <https://journals.sagepub.com/>
- Turney, K., & Goodsell, R. (2020). Marriage, family support, and rehabilitation among incarcerated individuals. *The Prison Journal*, 100(4), 560–578.
- United Nations. (2015). United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (The Mandela Rules) <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/standard-min>
- Walker, D., Bowen, N., & McKenzie, C. (2020). Psychological distress among newly incarcerated individuals: The role of environmental and social factors. *Journal of Criminal Psychology*, 10(3), 189–205.
- Wangmo, T., Handtke, V., Bretschneider, W., & Elger, B. (2020). Improving health in prisons: Exploring differing views of correctional staff and inmates. *Journal of Correctional Health Care*, 26(2), 146–157.